

IR4568-225-3-2, IR4625-269-4-2, IR5853-118-5, IR8192-200-3-3-1-1, IR9129-136-2, IR13419-113-1, IR13240-10-1-3-2, IR13423-17-1-2-1, IR14632-246-2, IR19743-46-2-3, B2149-PN-26-1-1, BPI R1-2, and IET 1444.

Fifteen rices were evaluated in replicated yield trials in the same field in each season. The plot size was 2 × 3 m in the first season and 3 × 4 m in the two other seasons. Cultural practices were the same as for the mass-screening.

Grain yields of seven selected rices and iron toxicity scores in three seasons are in Table 2.

In the 1979 dry season, IR4683-54-2

gave the lowest score (2.5) and the highest yield (4.5 t/ha); IR26, the susceptible check, gave the highest toxicity score (4.8) and the lowest yield (1.7 t/ha).

There were no other correlations between symptoms 4 weeks after transplanting and grain yield.

In the 1979 wet season, iron toxicity was severe because of soil acidification in the dry months preceding the wet season. The toxicity scores were high and the yields were low. But, IR4422-480-2, IR4683-54-2 and IR46, which were among the top yielders in the dry season experiment, also were among the best in the wet season. IR26, the sus-

ceptible check, and IR42 suffered severely from iron toxicity. Their maturity was so delayed that they could not be harvested with the rest.

During the 1980 dry season, iron toxicity was not severe (apparently due to the wet soil during the rainy months before planting), scores were low, and the yield was high. IR4683-54-2 was again the highest yielder. IR46 also showed tolerance for excess iron in both score and yield.

IR46 and IR4683-54-2 may be suited to acid sulfate soils in which the main growth-limiting factor is iron toxicity. ■

Decimal scoring systems for drought reaction and recovery ability in rice screening nurseries

G. C. Loresto and T. T. Chang, International Rice Research Institute

Tall traditional varieties differ from semidwarfs in their visible responses to water stress. In the past workers have often given more attention to drought resistance at the vegetative growth

stages than to responses at the reproductive phase, which is more closely related to grain yield. Recovery from drought stress also deserves attention. We have devised decimal scoring sys-

Table 1. Scoring^a system for drought resistance screening at vegetative phases I and II.^b IRRI, 1981.

Decimal score	Plant type	Stress symptoms			
		Leaf rolling	Leaf drying	Plant color	Growth stunting
1	Tall traditional types	Slight folding from early morning to late afternoon	No drying	Remains green	No stunting
	Semidwarf types	No rolling	Few leaf tips drying	Green	
3	Tall traditional types	Partial rolling from early morning to late afternoon	Few tips drying more than 1 cm in length; 5–10% basal leaves dried	Green	”
	Semidwarf types	No rolling	75% leaf-tip drying extended to 1/4 of leaf blade; 5–10% of lower leaves dried	Green	”
5	Tall traditional types	Complete and tight rolling from early morning to late afternoon. Partial unrolling when temperature cools during day; complete unrolling at night	Most younger leaf tips dried; 25–40% lower leaves dried	Unusually dark green	”
	Semidwarf types	Complete and tight rolling; partial unrolling at night	50% younger leaves with 1/2 – 1/3 area dried; 25–40% lower leaves dried	Ashen gray or yellow	Slight
7	Tall traditional types	Tube-like rolling; no unrolling at night	Most upper leaves with 2/3 – 3/4 area dried; 60–80% lower leaves dried	Ashen gray or yellow	Stunted
	Semidwarf types	Same as tall traditional			
9	Tall traditional types	Tube-like rolling; no unrolling at night	100% of all leaves dried; plants generally approach permanent wilting, some die	Meristematic tissues show a slight green to light green tinge	Severe stunting
	Semidwarf types	Same as tall traditional			

^aScores were taken 15–20 days from the start of imposed stress or when the susceptible checks showed symptoms of moisture stress. Preliminary scoring should be taken when plants show the first signs of stress. ^bVegetative phase I refers to the active tillering stage of both the early and late-maturing varieties, and ranges from 50 to 60 days after seeding (DS). Vegetative phase II applies only to the late-maturing varieties at about 80–100 DS.

Table 2. Scoring systems for drought resistance at reproductive phase, 12–15 days after start of stress.

Decimal score	Heading ^a	Panicle exertion	Panicle size	Spikelet fertility (%)	Grain filling	Leaf rolling
1	No delay	Full	Normal	91–100	Mostly well-filled	Slight folding
3	Delayed by less than 1 wk	Full	Normal	76–90	Mostly well-filled	Half-rolling
5	Delayed by more than 1 wk	Partial ^b	Slightly reduced	51–75	Mostly half-filled	Full to tight
7	Delayed by more than 2 wks	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	11–50	Half-filled to empty	Tight
9	No heading until soil moisture is replenished	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	0–10	Mostly empty	Tight

^aLate varieties usually recover and produce grains when the rains set in before the end of the test. Reproductive scores are usually less reliable for the late-maturing varieties when rainfall is frequent before the dry season ends. ^bExcept for inherent agronomic traits.

Table 3. Scoring system for recovery (scores taken 1 or 2 days after rewatering).

Decimal scale	Description
1	90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering (or a rain)
3	75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering
5	75-90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 3-4 days after watering
7	50-75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 4-5 days after watering
9	Fewer than 50% of plants produce new leaves or tillers 1 week after watering

tems that provide separate criteria for different variety groups, for responses at the vegetative and reproductive stages, and for recovery after rain (Tables 1, 2, 3). Our system should supplement the brief scales given in the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Studies on *Claviceps oryzae sativae*, the incitant of false smut of rice

R. A. Singh, presently senior postdoctoral fellow, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute; and R. K. Verma, Plant Pathology Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

Nutritional studies of the fungus *Claviceps oryzae sativae* showed that growth was maximum on yeast peptone potato dextrose agar, followed by that on oatmeal yeast extract, rice yeast dextrose, yeast extract, rice polish, Richard's, Lilly and Barnett's, Raulin's, Coon's, Leonian, Brown's and Czapek's agar. Seven carbon sources were tested. Growth was maximum on maltose followed by mannitol, galactose, starch, sucrose, lactose, and sorbose, and control. Among the nitrogen sources evaluated, asparagine supported maximum growth of the fungus followed by ammonium oxalate, ammonium chlo-

ride, potassium nitrate, peptone, control, sodium nitrate, and tris (hydroxymethyl) methylamine.

Eight isolates of the fungus collected from different parts of India were grouped into four strains on the basis of morphological and cultural characters. A cytological study of the germinating conidium indicated that mitotic division and germ tube formation occur simultaneously. Subsequent nuclear divisions occur quickly to meet the requirement of secondary conidia produced at the rate of 1 nucleus/conidium.

Survival studies of conidia, pseudosclerotia, and true sclerotia showed that the first two propagules do not survive for long either at room temperature or in the field and probably do not serve as the source of primary inoculum in northern India. However, true sclerotia survived sufficiently long at room temperature and in the field and probably act as the primary inoculum source.

Fungicidal evaluation in vitro showed

that Du-Ter, TCMTB, Brestanol, Aureofungin, and Difolatan were effective against the pathogen. Alkaloids were detected in both pseudosclerotia and true sclerotia, which gave positive test for a carbohydrate, glycolipid and for an unsaturated compound, but they differed on the basis of the presence or absence of aldehyde or ketones, or both. ■

Mechanical separation of paddy seeds as applied to plant pathology

K. M. Rajan, Rice Research Station (RRS), Moncompu, Kerala, India 688503

Two major plant pathological constraints in rice production in the Kuttanad tract of Kerala, India, are sheath blight *Corticium sasakii* and sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. Sheath rot is relatively new and is difficult to control through chemical means because it is seedborne.

Seed treatment with fungicides